

Design and Prototyping of a Ground-Aerial Robotic System

D. Kotarski, A. Šćuric, P. Piljek, T. Petrović

Abstract— This paper presents an investigation into the feasibility of using a ground-aerial robotic system for data collection missions. It outlines the design of a system consisting of a tracked unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) and a multirotor unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). The UGV is designed to enable the possibility of changing and charging batteries for the UAV, which is equipped with sensors for precise landing on the UGV platform. Rapid prototyping technologies were used to create a small experimental aircraft with a simple battery change airframe that can be tested indoors or outdoors. Parts of the chassis and drive elements were designed and manufactured for the UGV platform, and then the drive assembly and testing were carried out. The control systems of the UAV and UGV robots were evaluated through preliminary experiments. In future work, the integration of the control system and prototyping of the mechanism and electronics of the module for charging and changing batteries are planned in order to facilitate further advancements in the field of data collection missions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of mechatronic systems, especially various types of robots, has contributed to numerous applications primarily in the field of industry. From the aspect of outdoor operations such as surveillance or inspection and numerous others, large efforts have been made in hardware and software development with the aim of increasing system autonomy. Considering the environment in which they operate, mobile robots can be divided into unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs), unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and vehicles used in maritime missions. Recently, there has been an increasing emphasis on the integration of different types of mobile robots into heterogeneous robotic systems.

Given that the considered spectrum of missions includes stationary and moderate-speed movements and the possibility of vertical take-off and landing, multirotor type of UAVs are mainly used as aerial robots. There are numerous applications of multirotor UAVs, from mapping [1], surveillance [2], inspection [3], and many others. The most common aircraft configuration consists of four rotors, the so-called quadrotor [4]. The multirotor type is interesting considering the versatility that results from the number, type, and geometric arrangement of the rotors. This type of UAV is increasingly being used in the field of smart agriculture for missions involving content dispersal [5] and in missions involving cargo transfer [6]. The main disadvantage of this type of aircraft is high energy consumption, which results in reduced autonomy.

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Figure 1. UGV-UAV coordinate systems.

A heterogeneous group of mobile robots can be composed of several UGVs and UAVs that cooperate to perform a predefined mission. High-level algorithms for task and mission planning enable cooperation between UGVs and UAVs. One way of cooperative exploration is for the UGV to navigate through free space, while the UAV provides enhanced situational awareness through its higher vantage point in 3D space. In the paper [7], the navigation and stabilization scheme for 3D heterogeneous formations is presented, which enables relative localization. The so-called bird's eye approach was tested in research [8], where robot platforms suitable for executing indoor missions were used. A robotic team consisting of UAVs used for manipulation tasks and UGVs as help and assist robots was studied in the paper [9]. There is great potential for the application of aerial-ground systems for outdoor missions such as achieving autonomous inspection of energy infrastructure. In the paper [10], an innovative architecture of a heterogeneous system was presented and tested for the case of a detailed inspection of power lines. Furthermore, in the work [11], an integrated UAV-UGV system for data collection in construction applications was presented and tested.

The development of aerial-ground system hardware has enabled numerous applications that include the transfer of one robot by another, whether it is a UGV carrying a UAV or, in rare cases, a UAV carrying a small UGV. From the aspect of autonomy, the key operation is the landing of the UAV on the UGV, which requires the fulfillment of technical requirements. In the paper [12], a conceptual study of a smart landing of VTOL-UAV on a fixed station which can be also

Author D. K. is with the Karlovac University of Applied Sciences, 47000 Karlovac, Croatia (e-mail: denis.kotarski@vuka.hr).

Authors A. Š. and P. P. are with the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture, University of Zagreb, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia (e-mails: as239650@stud.fsb.hr, petar.piljek@fsb.hr).

Author T. P. is with the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia (e-mail: tamara.petrovic@fer.hr).

mounted on a UGV is presented. Furthermore, the UGV can be equipped with additional manipulators, which represent an autonomous system for docking. Such a system was presented in the paper [13] and tested using an indoor UGV robot and a quadrotor aircraft. Ground-aerial systems can be deployed for various tasks due to their superior efficiency, mixed capabilities, and shared sensor resources. There is great potential in the application for repetitive tasks such as wind turbine inspection.

In this paper, the concept of a ground-aerial robot system is presented, which can be suitable both for indoor and outdoor missions. The UGV platform was designed, which is based on the differential drive on which the tracks (caterpillars) are mounted. A module for docking the aircraft was considered, which consists of a mechanism for swapping batteries and a charging circuit. The prototyping of the drive elements and the UGV platform chassis, and also the quadrotor UAV was carried out, after which certain system features were tested. Preliminary tests of control modules have been carried out, and the next phase of research is moving toward the integration of the UAV and the UGV robot into a heterogeneous cooperative system.

II. GROUND-AERIAL ROBOTIC SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The main goal of the ground-aerial system is to increase the autonomy of the system, on the one hand, to save the operator's time, and at the same time to increase energy efficiency. Such a system can potentially be used in applications such as border surveillance, wind farm inspection, and even in a field of precision agriculture where content dispersal is included in the mission profile. In this research, a small-scale robotic system suitable for data collection missions is further discussed. From the aspect of system hardware design, there are two main elements, the UGV platform and the multirotor type of UAV.

A. Quadrotor UAV

In terms of control, multirotor aircraft represent an inherently unstable system, given that with the loss of functionality of the control loops, such an aircraft cannot independently return to the state of balance (hovering). The Cube flight controller (FC) with associated components was used in the research. For outdoor missions, a global navigation satellite system (GNSS) and precise RTK GNSS modules are considered for positioning, while a module with an IR-LOCK sensor is considered for precise landing. The mission profile determines the trajectory of the aircraft, whereby the state of the aircraft is determined by its position $\xi = [x \ y \ z]^T$ and orientation $\eta = [\phi \ \theta \ \psi]^T$ in 3D space. The kinematics of the aircraft $\dot{\xi} = \Theta \mathbf{v}$ is determined by the matrix Θ , which, using fundamental rotation matrices ($\mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$), maps the velocities \mathbf{v} from the aircraft body fixed frame (\mathcal{F}^B) to the velocities $\dot{\xi}$ in the base fixed frame from which the state of the aircraft is obtained $\xi = [x \ y \ z \ \phi \ \theta \ \psi]^T$, as shown in Fig. 1.

The multirotor UAV is a multivariable system described by a dynamic model of a rigid body with six second-order differential equations. The equations of motion can be derived using the Newton-Euler method assuming that the origin of the body frame coincides with the center of gravity, while the axes coincide with the main axes of inertia of the aircraft. The

acceleration vector, which is influenced by the forces and moments of the environment and the propulsion system, can be described by the following equation

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{M}_B^{-1}(-\mathbf{C}_B(\mathbf{v})\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{g}_B + \mathbf{d} + \mathbf{u}_B), \quad (1)$$

where the matrix \mathbf{M}_B contains mass and moments of inertia that provide resistance to motion, with the aircraft mass as a key parameter from the aspect of system design. This primarily results from the fact that in order to achieve a stationary state, the influence of the gravitational force vector should be canceled. Given that an aircraft can rotate in 3D space, $\mathbf{C}_B(\mathbf{v})$ represents the Coriolis and centripetal matrix describing inertial forces and moments. Other effects that affect the system dynamics, as well as external disturbances, are lumped into vector \mathbf{d} . The propulsion system of the multirotor aircraft is responsible for achieving the necessary motion, which is described from the dynamics aspect through the forces and moments of the propulsion system as a control vector \mathbf{u}_B .

The number of control variables depends on the configuration of the aircraft, which is determined by the geometric arrangement of the rotors. The matrix of the control allocation scheme maps the aerodynamic forces and moments resulting from the rotation of the propeller to the propulsion forces and moments of the control vector, where the angular velocities of the rotor are the inputs in the mathematical model. Conventional configurations are characterized by a planar arrangement of rotors, which come in pairs (CW and CCW), the most common being the version with four rotors, the so-called quadrotor or quadcopter. Assuming that the propellers are rigid and that the aerodynamic effects of each rotor consist of a thrust force that can be modeled as proportional to the square of the angular velocity ($f_{R_i} = k_{f_i}\omega_i^2$) and a drag moment ($\tau_{R_i} = k_{\tau_i}\omega_i^2$), the control vector of the quadrotor configuration (Fig. 2) that is planned to be prototyped is defined by the following expression,

$$\mathbf{u}_B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ k_f & k_f & k_f & k_f \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}k_{\tau}l \\ -k_{\tau} & -k_{\tau} & k_{\tau} & k_{\tau} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_1^2 \\ \omega_2^2 \\ \omega_3^2 \\ \omega_4^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 2. Schematic of UAV configuration.

Figure 3. Characteristics of EPU setups.

Such configurations represent underactuated systems, given that the number of control variables is less than the number of DOFs. In addition, fully-actuated multirotor UAVs such as configurations with passively tilted rotors [14], can perform more complex and precise movements.

Given that a small-scale system suitable for a data collection mission will be designed further, aircraft with a diameter of up to 0.5 m have been taken into account. To propel such aircraft, a combination of BLDC motors with $K_v > 1000$, propellers in the range of 3 to 10", and batteries with 3 to 6 cells are considered. From the point of view of design, it is important to emphasize that such UAVs are systems of high energy consumption, considering that rotary wings are used, which must cancel gravity force. The performance depends not only on the parameters of the propulsion system but also on the capacity and mass of the battery. Characteristics of 3 different electric propulsion unit (EPU) setups are shown in Fig. 3.

B. UGV platform

In the conceptual phase of designing the UGV platform, the main goal is to achieve scalability of the platform, and an additional goal is a reconfigurability. Primarily, the differential configuration of the drive module is considered, which consists of two sets of drive elements on which tracks suitable for outdoor terrain are mounted. Under the assumption that it moves on a flat surface, it can be said that this type of robot exists in two-dimensional space and has three DOFs, position (x, y) and orientation (ψ) . The kinematics of such a robot configuration can be described using the Unicycle-Type Wheeled robot model [15]. The arrangement of the drive enables rotation in place without changing position, and the rotational speed is determined by the differences in the angular velocities of the left and right actuators, on which, for example, a wheel or caterpillar drive element is mounted. Differential drive belongs to non-holonomic configurations that do not have independent control of each of the DOFs. Considering a reconfigurable platform, using two sets of differential drive and mecanum wheels, a holonomic configuration can be accomplished, a so-called omnidirectional robot suitable for indoor missions.

The UGV platform consists of a chassis on which a drive module is mounted, consisting of drive components and parts. A pair of IG52-04 24VDC 285 RPM gear DC motors driven by a Sabertooth dual 25A motor driver was selected. Given that the platform is intended to be used for outdoor missions, the molded track set from the manufacturer SuperDroid Robots will be used alongside other drive components. The torque is transmitted from the motor via a chain transmission

Figure 4. UGV topology.

to the drive element of the molded track. A shaft sprocket with 15 teeth is mounted on the motor shaft, which via single strand roller chain, ANSI #25, transmits torque to the roller chain sprocket with 25 teeth, which is mounted on the axle of the track's drive element. The energy circuit of the driver is connected to the LiPo battery, while the signals from the control module of the UGV robot come to the driver control circuit. The UGV platform concept consists of a docking module for a multirotor UAV whose main feature is a battery-swapping mechanism. In a nutshell, it is a 3-axis Cartesian robot whose task is to guide the battery. The docking module is connected to the control module of the UGV robot and is connected to the battery via the charging circuit. The topology of the UGV platform is shown in Fig. 4.

III. DESIGN AND PROTOTYPING OF UAV AND UGV PLATFORM

The development of the system is carried out in three phases, the design phase, the prototyping phase, and the testing phase. The design of a heterogeneous robotic system that is suitable for outdoor missions, especially for repetitive tasks, which, from the hardware aspect, consists of a quadrotor aircraft assembly and a UGV platform, is shown. In the system design phase, the most important step is the selection of the elements (components and parts) of the hardware. Additive manufacturing (AM) was considered for the production of parts that, together with components, make up the system assembly. Given that the considered system consists of modules, faster system development is enabled through the testing phase.

A. Design phase

To assemble the prototype, it is necessary to construct parts of the system that, together with the components, form a functional assembly. The Solidworks software package is used for the 3D modeling of the parts, whereby a .stl file is generated from the part model. Considering the complexity of the system, there are three main challenges. The first is the aircraft assembly, which should have hardware features that allow it to land on the docking module of the UGV platform. Furthermore, it is necessary to enable simple replacement of the battery or batteries, which directly increases the number of certain tasks that the UAV can perform, and additionally

Figure 5. Plug-in procedure for the UAV battery.

increases the overall efficiency of the system. Airframe parts will be designed considering the available rapid prototyping technologies. The procedure for connecting the battery module to the UAV assembly is schematically shown in Fig. 5.

The second challenge is the drive module of the UGV platform. Apart from the frame of the chassis, which is made of a welded steel profile, and axles with a diameter of 12 mm, the goal is to make the other parts using rapid prototyping technologies, which is a challenge considering the loads to which the chassis and drive elements are exposed. The parts of the drive module that are planned to be made using AM technologies have been designed, and the assembly is shown in Fig. 6. The drive module consists of a pair of tracks that are driven by the drive wheel, and rotate freely at the opposite end of the chassis via the auxiliary wheel that is mounted on a shaft. The axle bearings are connected to the chassis via frame parts and allow the track to be tensioned. On the other side, the drive wheel is mounted on a shaft that is driven via a chain transmission by a DC motor. Frame parts connect the axle to the chassis and the DC motor mount.

Going towards the mechanism of the docking module, which is responsible for changing the batteries, it is important to consider several design requirements. First, such a docking module with a mechanism should be able to be easily integrated into the UGV platform in terms of mechanical, electrical, and control connections. From the mechanical aspect, the mechanism is a 3-axis Cartesian robot, such as a 3D printer or a CNC router, which has the following tasks: pulling batteries from the aircraft, guiding to the charger station place, and pushing to the charger connector. The next step in the exchange is in the opposite direction, the mechanism pulls the battery from the charger place, guides it to the aircraft place, and connects the battery to the aircraft. The axes of the mechanism are parallel to the axes of the UGV platform. Special attention should be paid to the design of the y-axis mechanism, considering that the battery is pulled and pushed in this axis.

Figure 6. UGV drive module assembly.

B. Prototyping phase

In the prototyping phase of the UAV aircraft, two categories of technologies were used to produce parts. From carbon sheet materials of different thicknesses, aircraft parts are made using a 3-axis CNC router with a milling motor. The second category of technologies used in this research includes AM which will be used to produce parts of the aircraft frame and UGV platform. To produce parts that are not or are less mechanically loaded, fused deposition modeling (FDM) technology is considered, and the parts are made on the Prusa i3 MK3 low-cost FDM printer. Parts are created by extruding polymer filament through a heated nozzle onto a built platform, with PLA and PETG materials being used at this stage of research. For the production of mechanically loaded parts, continuous fiber fabrication (CFF) technology will be used, and the parts will be made using a Markforged Onyx Pro 3D printer, using micro carbon fiber-filled nylon matrix material and fiberglass reinforcement material. In addition, selective laser sintering (SLS) technology is being considered for the production of parts with complex geometries, where the hardware consists of a Sinterit Lisa Pro 3D printer and related equipment, while the models are prepared in the Sinterit Studio software.

And while from the point of view of making parts from carbon sheet material, the procedure is relatively simple, which boils down to the choice of tools and parameters of the router, with AM technology, things are more complex considering the number of 3D print parameters that can be adjusted. Depending on the AM technology, software tools are used, so-called slicers, into which the generated .stl file of one or more parts is read. In this step, the parameters of the 3D print are adjusted, for example in the case of FDM and CFF technology, the thickness of the walls and the type of infill, and additionally in the case of CFF technology the type of reinforcement. In the last step, the g-code is generated, which is then executed on the 3D printing hardware. After the printing is finished, some parts need post-processing for some prints. Part of the frame that was made with CFF technology on the Onyx printer using micro carbon fiber-filled nylon matrix and concentric fiberglass reinforcement is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Example of reinforced part manufacturing on Onyx 3D printer.

IV. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTS

After the successful testing of individual parts of the quadrotor system, the aircraft was assembled, and after sensor calibration, preliminary tests were carried out in the case of the remote control. From the perspective of the experimental framework, the PX4 ecosystem allows interaction with the MATLAB programming environment, which accelerates the development process of controlling such aircraft and adjusting parameters. From the aspect of multirotor firmware development, with regard to outdoor missions, it is necessary to consider more robust control algorithms. In addition to field tests, it is planned to use an indoor facility with cameras for which installation is planned with a setup that can produce an airflow of different amplitudes and directions. Preliminary testing of the experimental aircraft is shown in Fig. 8, which verified the assembly and framework for further implementation of control on other aircraft configurations and setups.

Given that the UGV platform consists of parts that are larger than the aircraft parts, it is important that individual modules can be tested separately, which speeds up the development process, given that the production of parts can be distributed. After the frame parts were manufactured, individual platform modules were assembled and tested. First, the parts of the frame consisting of the drive elements and the track were preliminarily tested. The tensioning of the track was done and the rotation of the track started by the drive wheel was tested. Then a pair of motors and elements were mounted, and preliminary testing of the drive configuration was performed. Experimental tests of the control system consisting of the GNSS module were then carried out, which is a prerequisite for further integration with the control system of the aerial system. Preliminary testing of the UGV platform control system is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 8. Preliminary testing of the custom quadrotor UAV.

Figure 9. Preliminary testing of the UGV platform.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a conceptual design for a ground-aerial robotic system to improve system autonomy and efficiency. The system design phase includes the integration of a quadrotor UAV and a UGV platform, making the system heterogeneous and scalable. The proposed design can be used for various missions, from data collection to cargo transfer, depending on the selected components and parameters. In the prototyping phase, parts of the small-scale system were manufactured using rapid prototyping for faster development and reduced costs. The hardware and software modules were tested during the preliminary experiments, which provided valuable insights for further testing. In future work, from the hardware aspect, the designing and prototyping of the mechanism and electronics of the module for charging and swapping batteries are planned, which will be followed by the integration of the control system.

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